

DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.6
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4955232
 UDC: 352.07
 JEL: O20

UNITED TERRITORIAL COMMUNITY AS A SUBJECT OF STRATEGIC TERRITORY DEVELOPMENT PLANNING

ОБ'ЄДНАНА ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНА ГРОМАДА ЯК СУБ'ЄКТ СТРАТЕГІЧНОГО ПЛАНУВАННЯ РОЗВИТКУ ТЕРИТОРІЇ

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Received 30.01.2021

Добрянська Н.А., Вечтомова Г.В., Добрянський Р.А. Об'єднана територіальна громада як суб'єкт стратегічного планування розвитку території. Оглядова стаття.

В роботі узагальнено сутність об'єднаної територіальної громади як суб'єкта управління соціально-економічним розвитком. Розглянуто стратегічне планування як складова цілісної системи планування місцевого розвитку. Висвітлюється та розкривається зміст та сутність поняття «територіальна громада» західними науковцями та українськими вченими. Зазначаються різні підходи до визначення сутності поняття «територіальна громада», серед яких: якісні, природно – географічні, етнографічні, соціологічні, економічні підходи, також розкриваються їх принципи та методи здійснення. Характеризуються ознаки територіальної громади як суб'єкта управлінням соціально-економічним розвитком. Проаналізована стратегія місцевого розвитку як багатогранне поняття. Проведено аналітичну характеристику результатів аналізу сильних і слабких сторін місцевого розвитку. Запропоновано довгостроковий план розвитку території, який охоплює всі основні аспекти місцевого розвитку. Пропонуються шляхи вирішення ключових проблем місцевого розвитку. Розроблено пропозиції щодо формування стратегічного плану розвитку територій об'єднаних територіальних громад та забезпечення їх економічного розвитку.

Ключові слова: стратегічний план, розвиток території, сільська об'єднана територіальна громада

Dobrianska N.A., Vechtomova H.V., Dobrianskyi R.A. United territorial community as a subject of strategic planning of territorial development. Review article.

The essence of the united territorial community as a subject of management of socio-economic development is generalized. Strategic planning as a component of a holistic system of local development planning is considered. The content and essence of the concept of "territorial community" with Western scientists and Ukrainian scientists are covered. Various approaches to the definition of the notion of "territorial community" are indicated, among which: qualitative, natural – geographical, ethnographic, sociological, ecological approaches, their principles and methods of implementation are also revealed. Characterized signs of the territorial community as a subject of management of socio-economic development. The Local Development Strategy is analyzed as a multifaceted concept. An analytical characteristic of the results of analysis of strengths and weaknesses of local development was carried out. The long-time plan for the development of the territory, which covers all the main aspects of local development, is proposed. We are offered ways to solve key problems of local development. Proposals for the formation of a strategic plan for the development of the territories of the united territorial communities and ensuring their economic development have been developed.

Keywords: strategic plan, territory development, rural united territorial community

The relevance of the study on the formation of a strategic plan for the development of a united territorial community is due to the need to bring it in line with the requirements of modern economic development. Strategic planning of the development of territorial communities is a systematic technology for the substantiation and adoption of the most important decisions on local development, the definition of the desired future state of the territory and the method of its achievement, based on the analysis of the external environment and its internal potential and is to form agreed with the territorial community of actions, implementing which efforts are concentrated, resources of basic subjects of local development.

The authorities at the local level have many problems associated with the economic inequality of joined villages, unemployment, abandoned infrastructure, with a lack of water resources, environmental pollution and unsatisfactory methods of garbage disposal.

Therefore, Strategic Planning It should be possible to apply an integrated systematic approach to local

development, to emphasize the competitive advantages of the community territories based on natural, material, financial, labor, social, intellectual resources, which, in the proper organization and integration, can be used for solving urgent local development problems.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Questions Research of the development of territorial communities as subjects of management of socio-economic development are devoted to the works of such scientists as M. Bimuratov, O. Batanov, O. Bobrovskaya, V. Kravchenko, G. Monastyrsky, O. Moroz, N. Oruda, V. Fadeev, Yu. Sharov and others. Insufficient development of theoretical and practical issues identified the choice of research theme.

The aim of the article is to improve theoretical and methodological principles and developing practical recommendations for the formation of a strategic plan for the development of a united territorial community in the conditions of local self-government reform.

The main part

One of the main issues that require consideration is the definition of the place and role of territorial communities in the conditions of domestic realities of economic development and taking into account the orientation for reforming the system of local self-government.

The term "territorial community" has entered the term "territorial community" entered the book of the Polish scientist Y. Spray "Elementary notions of sociology" as a synonym of the categories "territorial team" and "Local community". I. Schepan Territorial Community defines a group of people whose members are "tied to the lies of joint relationships to the territory where they live, and the lies of relations arising from the fact of living in a common territory".

Approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine April 1, 2014, the concept of reforming local self-government and the territorial organization of power in Ukraine provides for decentralization, creating proper material (property, in particular land owned by territorial communities), financial (taxes and fees related to the territory. the relevant administrative-territorial unit) and organizational conditions to ensure the execution of local self-government bodies of own and delegated powers [1].

The coverage of the concept of "territorial community" by Western scholars is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Illumination of the concept of "territorial community" by western scholars

The authors	The essence of the concept
T. Parsons	This is an association of existing individuals who have a certain territorial space as the basis for the implementation of most of their everyday activities
J. Hiller	This is a territorially separated association of individuals, firmly connected by social installations
B. Mercer	This is internally functionally linked to the association of people living in a certain geographic area at a certain time, have a general culture, form a certain social structure and reveal a sense of its unity as part of a separate group
L. Shnore	This is a collection of people who have a common permanent residence depends on each other in everyday life and carry out many activities to meet their economic and social needs
N. Smesler	For members of social communities are also characterized by a sense of belonging to a particular group (psychological characteristics), some general status

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2-3].

Out of table 1 shows that territorial communities have the right to dispose of land resources within their territory, unite their property and resources within the framework of cooperation between territorial communities to carry out joint programs and more effective provision of public services to the population of adjacent territorial communities. The main tasks underlying decentralization should be attributed: the transfer of powers from executive authorities to the level of territorial communities and consolidation of sufficient financial resources for them; a clear demarcation of powers between executive authorities and between different levels of local self-government bodies; Strengthening the responsibility of local self-government bodies for its decisions before voters and the state.

The Law "On the voluntary association of territorial communities" made it possible to begin to form a capable level of local self-government. From 2015 to 2018, 878 united territorial communities (OTG) were established in Ukraine. This OTG includes more than 4,000 former local councils. About 9 million people live in OTG. Such pace of inter-municipal consolidation international experts are called very high. The law also introduced an institute to OTG, representing the interests of rural residents in the community. In the villages of OTH, 786 Staroste work, and almost 1.7 thousand people perform the duties of Starost [4].

The coverage of the concept of «territorial community» academic period of independent Ukraine is given in Table 2.

From the above we can conclude: Ukrainian scientific thought of defining the concept of «territorial community», its place and role in the state mechanism is based on the views of European and American scientists, that is, to understand the community as an effective participant in socio-economic relations.

Table 2. Illumination of the concept of "territorial community" by Ukrainian scientists

The authors	The essence of the concept
N.O. Ore	The community that carries out its functions in various spheres of life, which is united by common interests and is formed within the limits of joint residence of people. A group of people who have the right to local self-government are recognized as a group of people and expresses its will in an independent decision of local affairs, the only appeal to state bodies and local self-government officials
M.O. Pukhtinsky	A deliberately formed, social and political active human community, self-sufficient in its existence and development in terms of providing financial, economic, natural resources
V.I. Kravchenko	A set of Ukrainian citizens who are jointly living in urban or rural settlement have collective interests and a legal status as defined by law; The territorial community can be considered as: Basic Administrative Territorial Unit; the form of organization of local authorities; The subject of civil-legal relations
M.A. Bemuratov	A set of individuals who are constantly inhabiting the relevant territory and are interconnected by territorial-personal relationships of a systematic nature
V.A. Grigoriev	Certain self-organization of citizens who are united by a territorial basis for the purpose of pleasure within the law of their collective needs and requests, as well as the protection of legitimate rights and interests
O.B. Batanov	This is the primary subject of local self-government, consisting of individuals - inhabitants (citizens of Ukraine, foreign citizens, stateless persons, refugees, forced migrants), which are constantly living, working on the territory of the village (or voluntary association in a common community of several villages), settlements or towns, directly or through their municipal structures, solve local issues, have common communal property, have a real estate in this territory, pay municipal taxes and related territorial-personal associations of a systematic nature

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5-7].

The study of the position of Western economists regarding categories «territorial community», «commune» and "social community" allows you to highlight as a minimum of five approaches to their characteristics (Tab. 3).

Table 3. Approaches to the definition of the notion of "territorial community"

Approaches to the definition of the essence of the concept of "territorial community"	
Qualitative	The community is considered primarily as a place. At the same time, questions of quality of life (housing, education, medicine, etc.) are considered.
Naturally – geographical	It is planned to study the community as a community in the natural geographic space. Attention is drawn to spatial placement, the influence of natural factors on the nature and conditions of activity, interconnections within the community and other communities
Ethnographic	There is a study of the community as a certain way of life with accentuation of attention on the cultural features of its development
Sociological	Community is seen as a social system. The prerogative in studying the phenomenon of the community is provided to the study of social relations characteristic of specific groups and larger social formations both within the community itself and in relations with the external environment
Economic	The interconnections of various sectors of economics, households and enterprises are studied. Attention is paid to the study of the professional composition of the population, the definition of sources and distribution of income, resources available in the territorial community

Source: authors' own development

So, from table 3, we see that there are 5 different approaches to determine the essence of the concept of "territorial community". A qualitative approach is characterized by the fact that in general, the community is considered as a place where the quality of life stands in the foreground. The natural geographic approach studies the community in space, where the spatial placement and influence of various natural factors are considered. The ethnographic approach is studying the community from the consideration of their features in cultural development. The sociological approach considers the community as a social system and investigates social relations. The economic approach is characterized by the study of interconnections of various sectors of the economy, households and enterprises.

Important was the use of a comprehensive approach to the definition of the essence of the territorial community, which category "community" or "commune" considered from five different positions:

- the first – determination of the legitimacy of the community as a historically formed community, with common culture, traditions and past;
- the second – the existence of a community as a system of interconnections between its members (family relationships, living in a common territory, belonging to a particular social group, etc.);
- third – the existence and activities of the community as a collective consumer;
- fourth – the need for functioning community to provide public services, participation of local social society institutions in life-supporting people and production processes;

— fifth – functioning of the community as a representative of the local population on the political arena and as a direct subject of management process.

Consequently, the territorial community is a naturally formed human community, whose members are individuals who live and work or own real estate in the territory within one or more settlements with a single administrative center, and characterized by a set of sustainable links and capacity to implementation of common interests in the issue of own life support and socio-economic development, acts as a representative of the local community and is the owner of communal property in the relevant territory.

Comprehensive analysis by domestic economists The concept of "territorial community", its definition, the study of the actions and opportunities of communities do not refute the fact that albeit in the legal aspect of the existence of a territorial community a substantiated and specifically defined framework of its functioning as a management relations and economic development. However In fact, the reform of the administrative-territorial system and financial decentralization of territorial communities possessed only "municipal legal capacity", having a complex of municipal rights and freedoms, but not realizing its owners of these rights and freedoms [8].

The right of territorial communities independently decide on local development issues defined by the Constitution of Ukraine and other legislative acts in most communities remained unrealized. Thus, the functioning of territorial communities on the territory of Ukraine was characterized by the following features:

- political uncertainty and instability, nucleate state of political relations at community level;
- undeveloped public sector;
- individualization and inclination of community members independently solve their problems;
- low level of confidence in the authorities and representatives of local self-government bodies, which are elected directly by members of the local community, etc.

Investigating the views of scientists in the issue of the allocation of basic features that comprehensively characterize the territorial community, as well as focusing on the tasks of administrative and territorial reform and decentralization, as a result, should allocate the signs of the territorial community (Table 4).

Table 4. Signs of territorial community as a subject of management of socio-economic development

The sign of the territorial community	Characteristics of the feature
Territorial	The territorial community is formed in a certain territory. Its members are individuals who live in this territory or work or possess certain real estate
Socio-psychological	The territorial community exists provided self-identification of each community member of its part and awareness of the commonality of interests
Historical and cultural	The community exists and develops in time, so when choosing the direction of its development it is necessary to take into account the historical aspects of the community's evolution, its cultural and custom characteristics that are characterized by the influence and the psychological climate in the community, and endogenous connections, inherent in the community
Political	The territorial community is the subject of legal relationship and representative of the local community on the political arena
Economic	The local community is the owner of communal property placed in its territory, and its members, in accordance with the newcomers, are tax payments to the local budget. The community functions to ensure its members with high-quality public services, may act as a participant in production processes and is a collective consumer, and functions to ensure its own capacity.
Nature	The territorial community is formed and operates on the basis of self-organization, social and economic activity and continuous development needs
Organizational and functional	The territorial community is a system with organizing political and social networks, which operates primarily on democratic principles of development and subject to its membership in solving their life support.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [8-10].

The state provides support for such communities in information and educational, organizational, methodological and financial forms.

In the method of forming capable territorial communities, which defines the mechanism and conditions for the formation of capable territorial communities and the procedure for developing and approving a promising plan for the formation of such communities. This normative act introduced the concept of a capable territorial community, which is defined as territorial communities villages (villages, cities), which as a result of voluntary associations are capable of independently or through relevant local governments to provide an appropriate level of service, in particular in the field of education, culture, protection, protection Health, social protection, housing and communal services, taking into account human resources, financial support and infrastructure development of the relevant administrative-territorial unit.

Thus, the united territorial communities received additional financial resources, expanded powers and direct intergovernmental relations with the state budget. Implementation of these powers based on the use of relevant

resources is the foundation on which the integral potential of the territory is formed and its use is provided to achieve the development of the territory. The key component of the integral potential of the territorial community is the financial and economic potential.

As you know, the first «boom» of the application in our country of strategic technologies to planning the development of territories refers to the mid-nineties of the last century and is associated with the formation of municipal movement, when local self-government has received additional rights that delivered local governments due to the processes of decentralization of public administration. managers before the need to realize the substantiated choice of areas of development of territories. Despite the first successes, after a certain period of time it was possible to state that the strategies of that period have not yet become real development tools, but gradually turned mainly to political documents, which mostly supported the electoral programs of various political forces. Among the reasons for such a situation can be distinguished objective and subjective aspects: to the first one should include the lack of development of methodologies of strategic planning, a certain simplicity of approaches and insufficient bases on objective development factors, namely, the main thing is the lack of responsibility for the effectiveness of strategies. To the second - insufficient readiness of public administrators to strategic activities, ignorance of their strategic thinking, technological competencies [11].

The second boom (approximately the end of the 90's of the last century is still) maintained by the development of a project approach in public administration, which absolute is corrected with advanced world and European trends. Thus, the European Community, placing the main responsibility for its own processes of development of countries, and accentuating on the results, provides fundamental attention to regional strategic planning [12].

The third wave of interest in strategic planning begins right today. It is generated by critical importance, uncertainty and complexity of processes of creating enlarged territorial communities, as well as multi-vector processes of the future (after consolidation) of community cooperation. All mentioned are influential factors of further development of approaches and technologies for strategic planning of territories.

One of the priority tasks after the establishment of an enlarged community is to develop a strategy for its development. It is obvious that if there were strategies for community development, which they must be revised, because the enlarged community has completely different resource opportunities, and therefore, other competitive advantages, based on which an updated strategic vision of development should be determined. an enlarged community and, accordingly, new priorities of development.

The fundamental role of a strategic approach manifests itself in the preparation of a leading document, on the basis of which consolidation of communities is carried out. It is a strategic plan developed by regional state administrations. The principle of voluntariness, which is based on the processes of community enlargement [13], in most cases leads to the transformation of this process to long-term. Accordingly, strategic plans developed today will repeatedly adjust during a period to obtain a certain steady state.

Figure 1. Local development strategy as a multifaceted concept
Source: compiled by authors on materials [13].

So, in fig. 1 shows the characteristics of the Local Development Strategy: it connects all parts of local development into a single whole, aimed at a long-term development plan of the territory, covers all major aspects of local development, gives answers to key issues of local development, ensures compatibility of all plans for the territory development, is The result of the analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of local development, the tax is a means of achieving the final result.

Strategic Planning is a systematic technology for substantiating and adopting the most important decisions on local development, identifying the desired future state of the territory and the method of its achievement, based on a situational analysis of the external environment of the territory and its internal potential and consists in forming agreed with the territorial community of action, in the implementation of which The efforts are

concentrated, resources of basic subjects of local development.

Strategic local development planning should be based on the principles of strategic planning of sustainable development of territories and a number of special principles (Table 5).

Table 5. Principles of strategic planning of local development

Principles	Signity of principles of strategic planning of regional development
Objectivity	Livestock to preliminary achievements, experience and objective information collected during strategy development
Goalposition	Clear Formation of Goals and Specific Strategic Goals
Effectiveness	Direction of all measures made to strategy to achieve their goals
Efficiency	Determination of quantitative expression ratio of expenses and results of improvement of economic and social status of the territory
Priority	Inclusion in the strategy of the main directions, the implementation of which will enable the harmonious development of the territory
Competence	Ensuring compliance with the issues that are directed to the strategy and competence of territorial development management bodies
Complexity	Creation of a diversified and innovative economic structure based on social consensus
Succession	Involvement in the process of developing representatives of all stakeholders in order to ensure heredity in implementing the developed strategy
Alternative	Exploring alternative strategy variants
Transparency	Provision of transparency of the processes of development and implementation of the strategy, wide coverage of them in the media, involving stakeholders to them
Situations	Detection, assessment, taking into account the influence of internal factors and external environment, possible development options, depending on their combination

Source: authors' own development

So, against the background of the use of the principle of voluntaries, serious substantiated strategic decisions on choosing a community or an independent way of existence or in combination with others. Analogues such a decision has not yet known the Ukrainian practice planning practice, which consequently, if not methodological weakness and preferred empirism used today approaches to the development of strategic plans.

Enlarged communities become largely comparable, which could not be said about former small communities. This extends the possibilities of benchmarking as a strategic development tool. Benchmarking is a comparison with advanced analogues (communities, territories, enterprises, organizations) [13].

Today, strategies should acquire a risk-oriented character, provide the most likely risks and try to prevent them from increasing the degree of implementation of strategic initiatives, that is, to have an anti-crisis character.

Classification of strategies of united territorial communities:

- Strategies of concentrated growth
- Integrated Growth Strategies
- Stabilization strategies
- Restructuring Strategies
- Strategies of diversified growth
- Reduce Strategies

It is integration of strategic and project approaches that makes a significant contribution to the implementation of such a task as a result of the fact that the integrated approach transforms a strategy to project portfolio and programs. In this case, the formation of each project involves an analysis of risks and the formation of a reaction plan. In order to use a strategy in the anti-crisis context, the mechanism for managing the implementation of the Strategy should provide for the diagnosed level of risks and crisis hazards of operational adjustment of the strategy (implementation of risks reaction plans) or changes in its composition. Thanks to the strategy orientation of the risks pre-determined in projects, the degree of strategy is increased. In addition, the solution of the same task contributes a system for monitoring the implementation of a strategy based on monitoring individual projects, and then - monitoring the execution of goals in the branches of the goals tree and to the strategy as a whole.

Complimenting communities are one of the key processes of reforming local self-government, but it only creates the potential of the normal functioning and development of territorial communities in which the leading place is occupied, in particular, the processes of community cooperation implemented by strategic planning and project approach tools [14; 16].

Consequently, the identification of the widespread capabilities of strategic planning in new conditions, working out its features in enlarged communities, further adaptation of project management technologies to local self-government environments are attractive spheres of perspective scientific interest, generate incentives for the development of methodology for developing and implementing strategies, project development projects.

Initiate the process of developing a strategy can any subject of local development. In initiative proposals, it is necessary to substantiate the relevance and utility of strategic planning for a territorial community, its view

regarding the developers of the Strategy, to identify possible obstacles to the introduction of strategic planning, ways to overcome them [14-15].

Figure 2. Scheme of the development of the strategy of united territorial communities

Source: authors' own development

Approximate composition of the working group (25-30 people): deputies of the local council; managers of departments (departments) of the executive committee; managers (representatives) of public organizations; representatives of local business; heads of public self-organization; representatives of local media; Other representatives of the local elite, regional development agencies involved experts, consultants.

Table 6. Levels of attraction of citizens to strategic planning and their characteristic signs

Level of participation	Characteristic features
Informative	Territorial community should be aware of what is going on
Advisory	The active part of the community should be able to make their proposals and have guarantees that these proposals will be heard
Partner	The competent part of the territorial community ("Local Elite") should be able to directly participate in the development and implementation of the Strategy

Source: compiled by the authors on materials [14].

The main criteria for which the collection of members of the working group are carried out:

- active participation in the socio-economic, public and cultural life of the territory;
- awareness of the local situation, the presence of intellectual, financial, institutional and creative opportunities, as well as the time and desire to actively participate in the development / implementation of the strategy;
- possibility of real influence on the local situation, interest in investing financial, material and intangible resources in order to implement programs and projects of local development.

Figure 3. Main features of the working group on the development of a strategic plan for the territorial community

Source: authors' own development

Strategic local development planning aims to solve one of the main tasks of any system: searching answers to the key points to which the available resources need to provide normal reproduction and development of the system of life of the territory.

The community profile should also be considered as one of the tools for providing a better access to credit sources or grants as well as investments. It is by this section that investors are often evaluated by the capabilities of the territory, its potential for calculations for the loans received. Investors are interested in the benefits of this territory over other possible places of investing their funds [17].

According to the results of the analysis, various variants of strategies, which are generally presented in Table 7, can be selected.

Table 7. Variants of strategies

Strategy	Combination of analysis elements
<i>Variants of strategies arising from analysis of strengths and chances</i>	
Strategy for strengthening / building	Concentration of attention on existing strong sides
Strategy use	Realization of favorable chances
Binding / correlation strategy	Relationship between existing strong sides and emerging chances
<i>Variants of strategies arising from the analysis of weaknesses and risks</i>	
Elimination Strategy	Eliminating the weaknesses
A minimization strategy	Minimization of risks
A transformation strategy	Convert weaknesses and risks to chances

Source: compiled by authors on materials [9; 13].

As a rule, the variants of strategies related to the use of strengths and chances (structures and use strategies) are more promising in terms of success than those arising from the analysis of weaknesses and risks. In the first case, the strategies are based on existing strengths, whose potential is not limited to, but when they are successful with new chances (strategy of bandaging / correlation) in the future can become a source of positive changes. This should be added that the implementation of such variants of strategies is usually associated with lower costs.

Conclusions

The territorial community is a naturally formed human community, whose members are individuals who live are working or owned by real estate in the territory within one or more settlements with a single administrative center, and characterized by a set of sustainable links and capacity to implement joint. Interests in the question of their own life support and socio-economic development, speaks a representative of the local community and is the owner of communal property in the relevant territory.

The main features of the territorial community are determined, namely: territorial, socio-psychological, historical and cultural, political, economic, natural, organizational and functional. In the context of the reform of the administrative-territorial structure and decentralization, this feature of the territorial community is defined as its ability, as the community acts as a subject to ensure the life of residents and social and economic development of the territory.

The formation of a strategic development plan of the territory of the OTG provides for the following priority directions:

- Development of the economy and filling of the community budget:
 - creation of favorable conditions for agricultural producers, small and medium-sized businesses in order to increase and create new jobs;
 - legalization of workplaces in order to increase the PIT;
 - creation of a favorable climate for attracting investors in tourism, agriculture, trade and industry;
 - development of a tourist industry to increase tourist collection;
 - Receipts to the community budget will work for community development and all residents;
 - Building a wholesale agricultural market;
 - control over the development of the territory (preventing theft of land);
 - control over the use of land plots of state and communal property
- Improvement of infrastructure and demonstration:
 - provision of garbage production services;
 - trimming of trees and purification of branches;
 - creation of a communal company for servicing plumbing and sewage networks;
 - repair of streets and municipal roads.
- Development of culture and art (establishment of work of cultural institutions and collectives of folk art).

The ability of a territorial community reflects its ability to accumulate and effectively use available financial resources, identifying and involving their reserves to ensure the implementation of current needs, the development of the territory and community competitiveness in the short and long term. A conceptual model for ensuring the capacity of a territorial community is substantiated, which allows to comprehensively assess the ability of a territorial community to ensure its development for a long-term perspective.

Abstract

The article summarizes the essence of the united territorial community as a subject of management of socio-economic development. Strategic planning as a component of a holistic system of local development planning is considered. Proposals for the formation of a strategic plan for the development of the territories of the united territorial communities and ensuring their economic development have been developed.

The purpose of the article is to consider factors that affect the implementation of approaches and technologies of strategic planning of territories as a result of the launch of the processes of reforming local self-government and consolidation of territorial communities.

The territorial community as a subject of local self-government implements a number of functions that are the main directions and activities of the territorial community to solve local issues. Functions of territorial communities are expedient to classify: according to objects (political, economic, social, cultural and environmental functions); According to subjects (functions of territorial communities villages, settlements, cities, districts in cities); Technological functions (financial and budget, material and technical, normological, informational, system-forming). Since the territorial community is a subject of management, it is expedient to allocate general management functions among technological functions: planning, organization, motivation, coordination and control. The classification, which includes object, technological and subjective functions of the territorial community as a subject of local self-government, allows, first, to reveal the activities of the territorial community, its orientation to a specific object. Secondly, the technology of realization of the functions of the territorial community is revealed. Thirdly, it finds its manifestation of specifics of specific actors - territorial communities villages, settlements, cities, districts in cities.

Consequently, an analysis of the characteristic qualities of territorial communities makes it possible to investigate the legal nature of these communities. We believe that the territorial community is the self-governing social center, the formation and optimal functioning of which will be a prerequisite for building civil society and the rule of law in Ukraine. The territorial community as a primary system-forming element of local self-government is primarily a «natural» corporate unit, whose autonomy is not from state power, but from the sovereignty of the people. The state only recognizes its activities implemented by residents - members of territorial communities as their natural social claim in one-way order, regardless of the degree of legal assumption. The state with the help of legal means only arranges the self-government activity of the local population without establishing it. It only sanctions municipal functions and powers related to regulating local life issues.

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Посилання на статтю:

Dobrianska N.A. United territorial community as a subject of strategic planning of territorial development / N. A. Dobrianska, H. V. Vechtomova, R. A. Dobrianskyi // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2021. – № 2 (16). – С. 49-59. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2021/No2/49.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.6. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4955232.

Reference a JournalArticle:

Dobrianska N.A. United territorial community as a subject of strategic planning of territorial development / N. A. Dobrianska, H. V. Vechtomova, R. A. Dobrianskyi // Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university. – 2021. – № 2 (16). – P. 49-59. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2021/No2/49.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.6. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4955232.

